

**UNIVERSITAS STUDIORUM FLUMINENSIS
UNIVERSITY OF RIJEKA**

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**GUIDELINES FOR ADDITIONAL CRITERIA FOR THE SELECTION TO
SCIENTIFIC-TEACHING, ARTISTIC-TEACHING, TEACHING,
ASSOCIATE, AND PROFESSIONAL POSITIONS OF ACADEMIC
STAFF AT THE UNIVERSITY OF RIJEKA AND ITS CONSTITUENTS**

Rijeka, October 2023

Pursuant to Article 12, paragraph 3, item 12, Article 39, paragraph 1, Article 40, paragraph 6, Article 42, paragraph 3 and Article 43, paragraphs 4 and 5 of the Act on Higher Education and Scientific Activity (Official Gazette 119/22), Article 34, items 1-2 and 25-27, Article 55, paragraphs 1 and 4, Article 56, paragraph 2, Article 58, paragraph 3 and Article 59, paragraphs 2 and 3 of the Statute of the University of Rijeka (CLASS: 030-01/23-01/05, REG.NO.: 2170-137-01-23-2, consolidated text of October 2, 2023) as well as Article 12 of the Ordinance on Scientific, Artistic and Innovation Activities at the University of Rijeka (CLASS: 030-01/23-01/16, REG.NO.: 2170-137-01-23-1 of September 22, 2023), the Senate of the University of Rijeka, at its 87th session held on October 17, 2023, adopted the following

GUIDELINES FOR ADDITIONAL CRITERIA FOR THE SELECTION TO SCIENTIFIC-TEACHING, ARTISTIC-TEACHING, TEACHING, ASSOCIATE, AND PROFESSIONAL POSITIONS OF ACADEMIC STAFF AT THE UNIVERSITY OF RIJEKA AND ITS CONSTITUENTS

General Provisions

Guided by:

- the public accountability and responsibility of all elements of its activities and the respective need for responsible, fair, open, transparent, efficient, and sustainable evaluation of merit-based academic work,
 - the internationally recognized excellence criteria in academic achievements, especially those in the European Research Area (ERA), as well as the need for international recognition and portability of jobs and associated career progression levels,
 - the provisions of the European Commission's Recommendation on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation, and entrepreneurial talents in Europe, and the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R), i.e., the new European Charter for Researchers,
 - its participation in the Young Universities for the Future of Europe (YUFE) European University alliance and in the Young European Research University Network (YERUN),
 - the development of the instruments of the open science system and University's endorsement of the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA),
 - the accession to the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA),
 - the strategic determinants of the University of Rijeka Strategy 2021-2025,
 - the recognized limitations of exclusively quantitative and bibliometric indicators of assessment of scientific achievements,
 - the recommendations adopted at the meeting of the International Scientific Council of the University, held on November 5, 2021,
 - the conclusions of the 4th joint thematic session of the Senate and the Council of the University of Rijeka on the topic 'The State and Perspectives of Scientific Development at the University of Rijeka', held on July 12, 2022, and adopted by the Senate of the University at its 73rd session held on September 20, 2022, and
 - the differences in academic work in the various fields and disciplines of science and art and at the different constituents of the University, as well as the differences in individual career paths,
- the Senate hereby adopts these Guidelines aiming at recognising, incentivising and rewarding all research¹, teaching, and institutional activities and results of the academic staff of the University

¹ The terms *research* and *researcher*, as used in this document, encompass all activities related to conceiving and creating knowledge (developing concepts, theories, models, techniques, instruments, software, operational methods, or creative works), both in science and in art.

of Rijeka and its constituents and the related career paths.

In addition to the mandatory legal and National criteria for the selection to scientific-teaching, artistic-teaching, teaching, and associate positions, the additional criteria for the selection to scientific-teaching, artistic-teaching, teaching, associate, and professional positions at the University or its constituents, in line with the aforementioned general provisions and the general evaluation elements defined below, as well as with the institutional specifics and the specificities of the various fields and areas of science and art, may be applied during the selection process for the different positions at the University and its constituents.

Elements for the evaluation

The general evaluation elements of the additional criteria for the selection to scientific-teaching, artistic-teaching, teaching, associate and professional positions at the University or its constituents will, as a rule, be classified into the following categories:

- applicant's academic knowledge and skills;
- skills and norms of academic and institutional behaviour; and
- personal qualities, knowledge, and skills.

The academic knowledge and skills will generally include:

- the qualitative level of scientific publications that cannot be assessed by bibliometric indicators, including the quality of the results, and the quality of the used research methodology;
- the acquaintance with the research methodology and technology;
- the work on multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, and transdisciplinary research and projects;
- the commitment to the internationalization of research and teaching activities;
- the commitment to open science practices: publications aligned with FAIR principles, openness of research data, of teaching resources, of project proposals, of software, codes, and hardware, of research methods, of reviews, the openness of scientific infrastructure, work on open innovations, the open community engagement, etc.;
- teaching competencies: planning, implementation, and development of teaching and learning materials, including studies in a foreign language, development of curricula and implementation plans, development of micro-credential modules, quality of mentoring, work on improving one's teaching and methodological skills, use of (open) e-learning tools, development of transferable skills of students;
- research management: planning, application to, and implementation of competitive scientific and artistic projects, planning and implementation of research and professional project activities, monitoring the career development of early career researchers, risk management, peer review activities in the assessment of publications, projects, study programmes and/or the quality of institutions;
- funding: attracting funding for research, knowledge commercialization, financial resources management, acquisition and management of research infrastructure, provision of funds for human resources (especially early career researchers);
- community engagement: entrepreneurial spirit, propensity towards entrepreneurship and knowledge transfer, development of innovation and cultural values, social and public sector innovation, addressing societal challenges, contributing to the development of regional innovation ecosystems, fostering civil science, knowledge of European and other international values and policies.

The skills and norms of academic and institutional behaviour, as a rule, will include:

- professionalism in work: commitment to the norms of academic integrity and work on the development and application of academic integrity, recognition of authorship of all contributors to the research results, contribution to gender equality measures, work in the field of intellectual property and copyright protection, confidentiality;
- leadership skills: successful management of the institution and/or of organizational units, quality of management of academic networks, research groups and projects, success in managing panels and commissions, talent recognition, management outside of the academic sector, work on the development of innovation hubs and contribution to networking with stakeholders from the economic, societal, and non-governmental sectors as well as from the wider community;
- work on the development and implementation of institutional policies, including contribution to institutional, regional, and national smart specializations;
- contribution to the achievement of the United Nations' Global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), to the objectives of the actions of the European Research Area (ERA) and of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) and contribution to institutional occupational health and safety measures;
- teamwork: respect for colleagues and associates, collegiality, people management, success in leadership of (international, intercultural, interdisciplinary) teams, collaborative and negotiating skills, fostering diversity and inclusion;
- communication skills: international and global action in research, teaching and institutional activities, cooperation with stakeholders in and outside academia, involvement in the work of societal and economic stakeholders, all forms of dialogue and cooperation with the wider community and citizens, building trust with societal stakeholders.

The personal qualities, knowledge, and skills will generally include:

- basic knowledge: the most important and up-to-date knowledge in one's research field, fundamental theoretical knowledge, knowledge application, the ability to search for and acquire information, information and data management, foreign language skills, academic literacy;
- enthusiasm, perseverance, integrity, self-confidence, self-criticism, responsibility, and independence, adaptability and flexibility, conflict resolution skills;
- cognitive skills: analysis and synthesis skills, abstract and critical thinking, strategic and systemic thinking, ability to cope with and solve problems and challenges;
- professional and career development: managing own career and planning its development, international, inter-institutional, and cross-sectoral mobility, continuous professional development in one's profession and teaching, professional networking and the establishment of professional networks, professional reputation;
- personal resource management: setting priorities, commitment to the profession, time management, work – to – life balancing, also in line with the principles of gender equality and the respect for diversity;
- creativity: intellectual curiosity, originality, innovation, argumentation skills, willingness to take intellectual risks, research independence;
- understanding different social and cultural contexts in own's and in the international community, awareness of the importance of the action for general societal benefit.

Assessment procedure

Based on the candidate's narrative curriculum vitae, the level of achievement in the aforementioned elements for evaluating the additional criteria for the selection to scientific-teaching, artistic-teaching, teaching, associate and professional positions at the University or its constituents will be assessed by the expert committees for job selection, setup in accordance with the Act on Higher Education and Scientific Activity. It is recommended that the level of achievement is assessed qualitatively by classifying it into basic, intermediate, advanced, and expert levels, whereby no candidate is expected to meet all the evaluation elements or to achieve the same level of accomplishment in all the evaluation elements.

It is recommended that the expert committees, as a rule, consist of a majority of members employed at reputable higher education institutions different from the one where the selection is taking place, preferably from abroad. Ideally, each committee member shall submit a separate (individual) written report with a reasoned opinion stating whether the candidate meets the legal and the National criteria for the selection to scientific-teaching, artistic-teaching, scientific, and teaching positions at the University, as well as the additional criteria in line with the Guidelines given herein. Based on the individual reports of all committee members, the chair of the committee prepares the final (joint) report and submits it to the Senate or, respectively, the faculty/academy/department committee.

Application of the Guidelines

The University of Rijeka Senate, or, respectively, the faculty/academy committees of the University constituents that are legal entities of their own, and the faculty/academy/department committees of the constituents without legal personality, to the extent appropriate and following their institutional specifics as well as the specificities of the respective areas and fields of science or art, may, based on the general evaluation elements given herein, define more precisely additional criteria for the selection to scientific-teaching, artistic-teaching, teaching, associate and professional positions at the University and its constituents. This should be done following the expectations from those involved in the academic work at a certain level of professional development, as well as from the function they aim at. In doing so, the possibility of flexible regulation of the division of employee's working time and obligations will be used and encouraged.

The University of Rijeka Senate, or, respectively, the faculty/academy committees of the University constituents that are legal entities of their own, and the faculty/academy/department committees of constituents without legal personality, will actively work to raise the awareness on the need to change the culture relating to the assessment of academic achievements, using in this frame the available communication and educational measures as well as, if deemed necessary, strengthening the corresponding institutional capacities. The responsibility of the heads of the constituents and of the organizational units for these activities is particularly emphasized, as is the need for the widest possible involvement of all stakeholders of the academic community.

Based on the experience of application at their institution, as well as on the exchange of experience with other institutions that qualitatively evaluate the academic achievements of their employees, the University of Rijeka Senate will periodically, and at least once every three (3) years, revise and improve these Guidelines.

